

DETERMINANT FACTORS OF THE PRIVATE EQUITY AND VENTURE CAPITAL INVESTMENTS IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

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Abstract

Purpose – The study aims to identify and analyze the factors that decisively influence the investments of private equity Funds (PEF) and venture capital Funds (VCF) in Central and Eastern European countries (CEE).

Methodology/approach – The link between PEF and VCF investments and a number of factors considered determinant is tested by using a sample of data from 11 CEE countries, data that were analyzed by descriptive statistics and econometric models, the chosen method being the one of the least squares.

Findings – The research results reveal that macroeconomic factors have a major impact on PEF and VCF investments. In addition to macroeconomic factors we have identified other country-specific factors that have a significant impact on PEF and VCF investments.

Research limitations/implications – In the conditions of more complex analyzes, on extensive databases, there is the possibility of determining other relevant factors.

Practical implications – The conclusions of this study can support the authorities to make informed decisions in order to stimulate foreign investment in the national and regional economy. At the same time, through the identified factors, the local Funds have at their disposal a relevant image on the investment context in the regional countries.

Originality/value – The study complements previous research, proposes new factors, puts together data and information on both PEF and VCF activity, most studies treating them separately.

Key words: Venture capital, Private equity, Innovation.

Introduction

Innovation is a key factor in stimulating sustainable growth and long-term competitiveness. Private equity (PE) and venture capital (VC) play a key role in supporting innovation and, implicitly, in mitigating global disparities in technological advancement. Through these operations, in the context of globalization, banks, investment funds, private entities get involved in local companies, in order to increase their value, through capital infusions, the use of new management strategies and/or the introduction of advanced technologies.

PE addresses long-term financial needs of companies in various stages of development with the main goal on increasing value through innovation. By implementing financial, operational and corporate governance strategies, the managers of PE entities contribute to the improvement of the financial statements of the acquired company. Unlike traditional sources of financing, through PE funding, an active relationship is created, in which the representatives of the investing entity collaborate closely with the existing management or with a new management team.

The main component of the PE activity, the VC activity, represents those operations aimed at financing start-ups and risky young companies but with great potential for growth and innovation.

In this case, the investing entity holds a minority stake and the degree of involvement is passive (advisory role, know-how, business relations). Unlike VC activity, in the case of another component of PE activity, namely the buyout activity, the representatives of the investing entity are actively involved in the company, sometimes even generating its restructuring.

Financing through PEFs and VCFs allows companies to prioritize long-term growth, with positive effects on their financial performance.

Regarding innovation, according to the latest data published by the European Commission in the European innovation scoreboard, Romania is part of the last category, that of „modest innovator”, among other CEE countries.

Given the context of globalization and the importance of PE and VC investments in supporting innovation, this study focuses on identifying the factors that PEFs and VCFs take into account in financing companies in Eurozone countries but which in the same time are geographically located in CEE.

Theoretical background

The factors that have a decisive influence on PE and VC investments have been the subject of studies and research conducted by a number of researchers in recent years. We note some of these that we considered relevant for this research.

Romain and La Potterie (2004) have identified the following determinants of VC investment: GDP growth, Interest rate, Labour market rigidities, Level of entrepreneurship, Number of triadic patents, R&D expenditures. Félix et al. (2007) argue that GDP growth, interest rate, stock market growth and venture capital divestments significantly and positively influence VC investments. Cherif and Gazdar (2011) indicate that GDP growth, unemployment rate, Stock market capitalization, R&D expenditures are the main factors influencing VC investments. Félix et al. (2012) analyze the influence of GDP growth, long term interest rate, stock market capitalization growth, IPOs, R&D expenditure, unemployment rate, market-to-book ratio, total entrepreneurial activity index and size of the M&A on VC investments. Bernoth and Colavecchio (2014) conclude that GDP growth, unemployment rate, inflation rate, stock market capitalization, labour costs, the institutional and legal environment are determinants of PE investments. Groh and Wallmeroth (2016) indicate that M&A activity, legal rights and investor protection, innovation, intellectual property protection, corporate taxes și unemployment rate have an impact on VC. At the same time, the authors pointed out that the determining factors can vary depending on the stage of development of a country. Precup (2017) analyzes the influence of GDP growth, market capitalization, R&D expenditures, interest rate, Unemployment rate, Productivity and Corruption on VC investments and leveraged buyout.

Other relevant studies that analyze the influence of VC investment determinants are those performed by Gompers and Lerner (1999), Jeng and Wells (2000), Schertler (2003), Leleux and Serlemont (2003) and Marti and Balboa (2001) analyze the determinants of PE investments.

Data and variables

This Study is performed on a sample of data from 11 countries in Central and Eastern Europe (Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia), valid for the period 2011-2018.

Several data sources were used in the study. Data on the volume of PEF and VCF investments were collected from the Invest Europe Association. Data on the volume of M&A transactions were collected from The Institute of Mergers, Acquisitions and Alliances (IMAA). Information on EIF's Private Equity and Venture Capital Funds Investments was taken from the European Investment Fund. The following data was collected from The World Bank: GDP growth, High-technology exports, ICT goods, Patent applications, R&D expenditure, Foreign direct investment, Time required to start a business, Stock market return. The following data were collected from Eurostat: Business enterprise R&D expenditure

in high-tech sectors, Innovation Index, Interest rate. The Credit - Market sophistication indicator was taken from the Global Innovation Index.

The variables that were analyzed in this study were the following:

European Investment fund (EIF). By developing and offering financial products to its intermediaries, the EIF improves SMEs' access to finance. EIF works with VC funds, which act as intermediaries and invest in innovative high-tech SMEs in the early and growth stages. Therefore, we consider that the activity of the EIF in financing SMEs should be a determining factor of PE and VC investments in CEE countries.

M&A Investment Volume. This variable represents the volume of mergers and acquisitions transactions in a year, for each country as a percentage of the country's GDP. Groh and Wallmeroth (2016) and Félix et al. (2012) have shown a positive influence of the volume of M&A transactions on VC investments. We expect that an active M&A market to have a positive impact on PE and VC investments.

GDP growth. Calculated as a percentage change from the previous year of GDP, this variable is a measure of economic activity. Gompers and Lerner (1999), Romanin and de la Potterie (2004), Félix et al. (2007), Cherif and Gazdar (2011), Félix et al. (2012) and Bernoth and Colavecchio (2014) have indicated a positive influence of GDP growth on VC investments in developed countries in Western Europe and the United States. On the other hand, Jeng and Well (2000) and Marti and Balboa (2001) consider that GDP growth is not a determining factor of VC investments. Precup (2017) has obtained mixed results, GDP growth has a positive impact on VC investments, but is not a significant factor for leveraged buyout investments.

High-technology exports. Calculated as a percentage of manufactured exports, this variable represents products such as computers, electric machines, products from the aerospace industry as well as scientific instruments and pharmaceuticals. All these products have in common the fact that they were produced with high research and development expenditures. This study will test whether High-technology exports are a determining factor in PE and VC investments.

ICT goods exports. Calculated as a percentage of total goods exports, this variable represents the export of *Information and communication technology* goods. This study will test how this variable will influence PE and VC investments.

Foreign direct investment, net inflows. This variable represents the new investment flows of foreign investors as a percentage of the GDP of the country in which those investments are made.

In this study we will test the positive link between foreign investment and PE and VC investments.

Patent applications, residents. This variable represents the patent applications registered by residents for exclusive rights to an invention. Romain and La Potterie (2004) and Schertler (2007) indicate a positive influence of patent applications on VC investments. This study will also test a positive influence of patent applications on PE and VC investments.

Research and development expenditure. The variable represents the total value of domestic research and development expenditure as a percentage of GDP. Among the authors who have demonstrated a positive influence of this factor on VC investments are Gompers and Lerner (1999), Schertler (2003), Romain and La Potterie (2004), Schertler (2007), Cherif and Gazdar (2011) and Félix et al. (2012). Although, Precup (2017) obtained mixed results, showing a positive impact on VC investments and a negative impact on leveraged buyout. This study will test a positive influence of R&D expenditure on PE and VC investments.

Business enterprise R&D expenditure in high-tech sectors. High-tech has long been considered a key factor in the sustainable growth of economic activity and business enterprise R&D expenditure is a determining factor of the high-tech sectors. Knowing that PE and VC investments contribute to the stimulation and development of innovation activity, we will test the positive link between this variable and PE and VC investments.

Innovation Index. Based on the European Innovation Scoreboard, this indicator reflects research and innovation performance, including other indicators such as: Human resources, Attractive research systems, Innovation-friendly environment, Finance and support, Firm investments, Innovators, Linkages, Intellectual assets, Employment impacts, Sales impacts. Groh and Wallmeroth (2016) studied

the influence of innovation on VC investments, they obtained positive results. This study will test the positive link between this variable and PE and VC investments.

Interest rate. This variable represents the long-term interest rate. Romain and de la Potterie (2004) and Félix et al. (2012) indicate that the long-term interest rate has a positive influence on VC investments. On the other hand, Gompers and Lerner (1999) indicate that short-term interest rate has a negative influence on VC investments. Romain and La Potterie (2004) argue that both, the short-term interest rate and the long-term interest, rate have a positive influence on VC investments. A positive influence was also obtained by Félix et al. (2007). Precup (2017) indicates that the interest rate positively influences PE investments but is not a significant factor for leveraged buyout investments. In their research, Cherif and Gazdar (2011) have shown that the interest rate is not a relevant factor for VC investments.

Stock market return. This indicator provides us information regarding the development of the stock market. Gompers and Lerner (1999), Félix et al. (2007), Schertler (2003), Cherif and Gazdar (2011) confirm a positive influence of stock market development on VC investments and Bernoth and Colavecchio (2014) confirm a positive influence on PE investments. Precup (2017) finds that market capitalization has a positive influence on leveraged buyout investments and a negative influence on VC operations. A negative influence of stock market capitalization growth on VC operations is also found by Félix et al. (2012). On the other hand, Jeng and Wells (2000) consider that the development of the stock market is not a determining factor of VC investments. This study will test the positive influence of stock market development on PE and VC investments.

S&P Global Equity Indices. This indicator measures the change in the price of the US dollar in the stock markets covered by country indices Standard & Poor's Global Equity Indices and Standard & Poor's Frontier Broad Market Index and is an important measure of overall performance. This study will test whether the S&P Global Equity Indices has an influence on PE and VC investments.

Time required to start a business. This is a Business Environment Measurement Indicator and represents the number of calendar days needed to complete the legal procedures for setting up a business. A high level of this indicator is expected to negatively affect PE and VC investments.

Credit. Granted as a score for each country, from 0 to 100, this indicator reflects market so-phistication from the perspective of ease of getting credit, domestic credit to private sector and microfinance institutions' gross loan portfolio. This study will test whether market sophistication influences PE and VC investments.

Statistical methodology and empirical analysis

The methodology used to estimate the econometric models by the least squares method involves several stages. Unit root tests were used to verify the stationarity of the variables. The selection of the type of unobservable effects was made based on the Hausman Test. The hypothesis of independence of the factorial variables is verified by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor indicator. Through the Jarque-Bera Test it was checked whether the residuals are normally distributed. Heteroskedasticity testing was performed with White's Test and to analyze the existence of a correlation between the errors of the econometric model, Durbin-Watson Test and Correlogram Test were applied.

In order to reveal the determinants of PE investments, after going through the above stages we estimated the following models:

Model (1):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot RD_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot Patent_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot ICT_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (2):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot Patent_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot Innovation_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot ICT_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (3):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot RD_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot Patent_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot EIF_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot GDP_{i,t} + \beta_5 \cdot ICT_{i,t} + \beta_6 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \beta_7 \cdot S\&P_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (4):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot RDH_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot Patent_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot M\&A_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot ICT_{i,t} + \beta_5 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (5):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot M\&A_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot FDI_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot Rate_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \beta_5 \cdot Credit_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (6):

$$PE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot M\&A_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot FDI_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot PE(-1)_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

The determinants of VC investments are highlighted by estimating the models below:

Model (7):

$$VC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot RD_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot Stock_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot Credit_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot VC(-1)_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Model (8):

$$VC_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 \cdot RD_{i,t} + \beta_2 \cdot GDP_{i,t} + \beta_3 \cdot Rate_{i,t} + \beta_4 \cdot Time_{i,t} + \beta_5 \cdot Stock_{i,t} + \beta_5 \cdot High_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Table 1 presents the results of the estimated models (1)-(6) which reveal the impact of determinants on PE investments.

Table 1. Determinant factors of the private equity investments

	Model (1)	Model (2)	Model (3)	Model (4)	Model (5)	Model (6)
PE (-1)						-2.314018 (0.0244)
R&D exp.	2.891172 (0.0038)		3.734002 (0.0004)			
R&D exp in high-tech				2.493451 (0.0148)		
Patent	2.070359 (0.0418)	3.468209 (0.0009)	3.500530 (0.0008)	1.216812 (0.2274)		
Innovation		3.781279 (0.0003)				
M&A				2.321731 (0.0229)	2.220920 (0.0301)	2.244799 (0.0287)
EIF			2.039036 (0.0455)			
FDI					2.675675 (0.0096)	2.335764 (0.0231)
GDP			-1.735777 (0.0873)			
ICT	-2.61911 (0.0106)	-3.596224 (0.0006)	-2.476713 (0.0159)	-2.020009 (0.0469)		
Rate					2.960612 (0.0044)	
Time	-3.554691 (0.0007)	-3.364113 (0.0012)	-4.610817 (0.0000)	-2.965293 (0.0040)	-2.513162 (0.0147)	-1.288245 (0.2030)
S&P			-1.168024 (0.2471)			
Credit					-2.784689 (0.0072)	
Constant	-0.518164 (0.6058)	-3.939815 (0.0002)	0.721623 (0.4731)	1.531678 (0.1298)	2.532023 (0.0140)	-1.691490 (0.0963)
R-squared	0.220198	0.282535	0.381225	0.224651	0.854989	0.823509
F-statistic	5.435747	7.580562	5.720893	4.404083	25.26874	18.66408
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000658	0.000033	0.000035	0.001417	0.000000	0.000000
Cross-section effects	random	random	random	random	fixed	fixed
Period effects	none	none	none	none	none	none

Analyzing the results of the estimated models presented in Table 1, we can conclude that the determinants of PE investments are R&D expenditure, Business enterprise R&D expenditure in high-tech, Patent, Innovation, M&A, EIF, FDI, Interest rate, ICT, Time și Credit. The first eight factors have a positive influence on PE investments and the last three have a negative influence. These models did not validate a statistically significant link between GDP growth and S&P Global Equity with PE investments.

The results of the estimated models (7) and (8) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Determinant factors of venture capital investments

	Model (7)	Model (8)
VC (-1)	1.161434 (0.8723)	
R&D exp.	2.677953 (0.0096)	2.174094 (0.0343)
GDP		2.692157 (0.0095)
Rate		2.951630 (0.0047)
Time		-2.993753 (0.0042)
Stock market return	2.291993 (0.0255)	1.731652 (0.0893)
Credit	-0.522512 (0.6033)	
High-technology exports		1.214744 (0.2300)
Constant	-0.918613 (0.3620)	-2.281478 (0.0266)
R-squared	0.89467	0.921517
F-statistic	35.79619	40.70405
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000	0.000000
Cross-section effects	fixed	fixed
Period effects	none	none

The analysis of the results of the estimated models presented in Table 2 indicates that R&D expenditure, GDP grow, Interest rate, Stock market return and Time significantly influence VC investments (the first four factors have a positive influence and the last factor has a negative influence). Credit and High-technology exports factors were not statistically validated.

Conclusions

The conclusions of this study are relevant for all PE and VC activity. Given that the largest share in the activity of PE and VC is the activity of the Funds, the influence of the determined factors is more important for them.

Processing the statistical models, several determining factors were identified for this activity, some of them being in fact reconfirmed and others new, obtained through statistical correlations, being proposed as determinants for PE and VC activity. These new factors identified are: EIF activity, FDI, ICT, Business enterprise R&D expenditure in high-tech, Time required to start a business (Time) and Credit - market sophistication (Credit). EIF, FDI and R&D in high-tech factors have a positive influence on PE investments while ICT, Time and Credit factors have a negative influence. Although, the Credit factor was not statistically validated as a determining factor of VC investments. For GDP grow and stock market development indicators, factors reported in previous studies, we obtained mixed results, so that these variables positively influence VC investments but a significant link between these factors and PE investments was not validated.

From the perspective of the science and innovation, the results of the study highlighted that there is a direct, positive link between the variables Innovation, R&D expenditure and Patent and the PE and VC investments.

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